

Embracing Diversity: Promoting Safe Space for LGBTQIA+ College Students in a Local College

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Abstract

This study examines the importance of creating safe spaces for LGBTQIA+ college students, with a focus on a local college setting. A positive school climate is essential for optimal learning, where all students feel safe, supported, and included. However, LGBTQIA+ students often encounter more challenges and hostility than their heterosexual peers due to the prevalence of heteronormative practices, policies, and curricula in educational institutions. These environments can lead to negative outcomes for LGBTQIA+ students, including adverse mental and physical health, social isolation, and lower academic performance. To address these issues, schools must implement strategies that challenge heteronormativity, such as zero-tolerance policies against discrimination, inclusive curricula that reflect diverse sexual orientations and gender identities, and mandatory professional development for educators to recognize and support LGBTQIA+ issues. This study aims to explore the perceptions of LGBTQIA+ college students regarding the existence and adequacy of safe spaces within their college. Through understanding these perceptions, the study seeks to advocate for necessary changes in policy and practice to foster a supportive and inclusive environment. The findings are intended to inform educational leaders and policymakers about the critical role of safe spaces in promoting the well-being and academic success of LGBTQIA+ students. Creating inclusive and supportive environments is not only a matter of equity but a fundamental right for all students to thrive academically, physically, and social-emotionally.

Keywords: LGBTQIA+, inclusivity, curriculum, safe space, local college

Introduction

Positive school climates foster an optimal learning environment in which students feel safe and supported, and are in a greater position to thrive in terms of academic performance, better relationships with peers and staff, and overall social-emotional well-being. Lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, or queer (LGBTQIA) students often have to navigate more challenges and hostile school climates compared to their heterosexual peers because school practices, policies, and curricula tend to prioritize heteronormative structures. Significant work is required to challenge these structures, such as by implementing zero-tolerance policies, LGBTQIA-inclusive curricula and mandatory professional development for educators, and by creating safe spaces for LGBTQIA students within schools. All students have the right to feel included, respected, and safe in a school environment. However, schools can be a hostile and lonely environment for students who identify as lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, or queer (LGBTQIA). LGBTQ youth are more likely to report feeling that schools are unwelcoming or unsafe due to unsupportive peers, staff, and policies (Colvin et al.). Compared to the heterosexual student population, LGBTQ students experience worse outcomes in mental and physical health as well as education (Snapp et al., 2015). Schools have a responsibility to create a safe and inclusive environment that supports LGBTQIA students academically, physically, and social-emotionally. However, heteronormative structures that exclude the LGBTQIA student population, lack of supportive policies that offer protection, and unsupportive/untrained teachers contribute to hostile learning environments. Challenging heteronormativity by the implementation of zero-tolerance policies, LGBTQIA-inclusive curricula, and mandatory professional development for educators, and creating safe spaces within schools, will promote a positive school climate for LGBTQIA students. The objective of this study is to assess the perceptions of LGBTQIA+ college students regarding the existence and adequacy of safe spaces within the college. Understanding its significance is crucial to

advocate for change, and skill-building in recognizing and handling LGTBQ issues and to respond to any forms of victimization such as bullying, harassment, or discrimination.

Research Questions

1. How do LGBTQIA+ college students perceive the current safe space in place?
2. What are the key challenges faced by LGBTQIA+ college students in accessing safe space and supportive environments within the college setting?
3. What strategies and initiatives have proven to be effective in promoting inclusivity for LGBTQIA+ college students, and how are they perceived by students?

Related Literatures

The study of Beasy et al. (2021). indicates that creating safe and inclusive environments for LGBTQ students in colleges is crucial for improving their educational outcomes, mental health, and overall well-being. The research shows that creating safe and welcoming spaces for LGBTQ students in colleges helps them do better in school and feel happier and healthier overall. Recent studies reveal mixed perceptions of campus inclusivity and safety among LGBTQIA+ college students. While some institutions show increased awareness and resources for sexual and gender diversity (Tinoco-Giraldo et al., 2021). The study of McClellan et al. (2022), LGBTQ college students desire more representation and community on conservative campuses, experience homophobia, transphobia, and discrimination, and have mixed feelings about the Safe Zone program. A study of Woodford et al. (2018) highlighted that there are specific campus policies and resources promoting LGBTQ+ inclusion that are associated with less discrimination and better psychological well-being for LGBTQ+ college students. Key strategies for fostering inclusivity include providing safe spaces, promoting student awareness and acceptance of diversity, and challenging heteronormativity through formal policies and procedures (Steck & Perry, 2018).

Allen et al. (2020) noted that LGBTQIA+ students face significant challenges in educational settings, including discrimination, fear of coming out, and lack of inclusive facilities. To address these issues, safe spaces are crucial for supporting LGBTQIA+ youth in schools and communities (Vaccaro et al., 2011). According to Gacita et al. (2017), implementing safe space training programs can improve attitudes and skills among faculty, staff, and students, promoting a more inclusive environment. A study by Steck et al. (2018) highlighted that creating a safe and inclusive environment for LGBTQ students requires providing safe spaces, promoting diversity awareness, and challenging heteronormativity through formal policies and procedures. LGBTQ college students experience marginalization within campus spaces, as traditionally heterogenous institutions uphold discourses that perpetuate unwelcoming environments for LGBTQ communities (Pryor, 2018).

Research indicates that various strategies can effectively promote inclusivity for LGBTQIA+ college students. Playful activities like gaming groups, LEGO sessions, and identity-focused video projects have been shown to build community and confidence among LGBTQIA+ students (Whitley et al., 2021). Structural initiatives, such as comprehensive non-discrimination policies, LGBTQ courses, and student organizations, are associated with reduced discrimination and improved psychological well-being (Woodford et al., 2018). Dedicated queer-inclusive spaces, mentoring, counseling, and peer programs are also beneficial, though often inaccessible to LGBTQ+ students from diverse ethnic backgrounds (Raja et al., 2023). Safe zones and affirming activities can support LGBTQ and perceived-LGBTQ students (Hernandez et al., 2020).

LGBTQ college students at a conservative campus want more representation, community, and inclusive policies despite the presence of some support programs (McClellan, 2022). Despite these efforts, LGBTQ students continue to experience high levels of harassment, highlighting the need for ongoing improvement in inclusivity initiatives (Hernandez et al., 2020).

Methodology

This study employed a case study approach to explore the lived experiences and perceptions of LGBTQIA+ students regarding inclusivity and safe spaces at public local college in Cebu. Semi-structured interviews were conducted to gather in-depth qualitative data, providing flexibility and adaptability in exploring these complex issues.

The research took place at Lapu-Lapu City College, public local college in Cebu, Philippines, an institution established to provide accessible education. The study focused on students from the College of Education, which offers various undergraduate programs.

The study utilized purposive sampling, selecting 10 LGBTQIA+ undergraduate students from the College of Education. This sampling method ensured the inclusion of participants who could provide relevant and detailed insights, based on their direct experiences. The selection was guided by the principle of data saturation, aiming for comprehensive coverage of the topic without emerging new themes.

A modified standardized questionnaire was used, based on items adapted from Ohlson's (2022) study on LGBTQIA+ students' perceptions of campus climate. The questionnaire was tailored to the local context, focusing on the participants' views on existing safe spaces, challenges in accessing supportive environments, and perceptions of inclusivity initiatives at the college. This instrument facilitated the collection of context-specific data, allowing for meaningful analysis and comparison with broader findings in similar research.

During the analysis phase, the transcripts were reviewed and coded to identify common themes and patterns. The data was analyzed using a thematic analysis approach, which involves identifying and categorizing themes that emerge from the data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The themes were then used to construct a rich description of the experiences of the LGBTQIA+ college students.

Ethical Considerations

Research demands not only expertise and effort but also a commitment to integrity and ethical responsibility. Throughout this study, ethical considerations were rigorously examined to ensure the protection of participants' rights. Measures were taken to maintain confidentiality and respect the privacy of all subjects involved.

Results and Discussion

This study anchors to support the data from the phenomenological research focusing on the lived experiences and perceptions of LGBTQIA+ students regarding inclusivity and safe spaces. The conduct of the study generated amount of data that are relevant and can be used to support further details for the students:

The researchers utilized a case study research design for the qualitative phase, Case studies are a versatile research method for in-depth exploration of bounded educational phenomena, such as programs, schools, or organizations (Dawidowicz, 2011). The major concern of case study analysis is to understand participants' views on existing safe spaces, challenges in accessing supportive environments, and perceptions of inclusivity initiatives at Lapu-Lapu City College.

Categorization of Data

The data were grouped according to the responses of the participants and identified the common answers to come up with the essential themes. These data were arranged and organized based on the common or general concepts presented by the participants. Regrouping was done to reduce the essential themes. The main themes into fewer items. The process finally generated essential themes. The second sets of data were the important phrases that emerged from the transcripts and comments were identified as thematic statements.

The key informants and participants answered the same sets of questions with a strong determination. We were able to find our informants through students from the College of Education, which offers various undergraduate programs. The meeting with our respondents was arranged during their vacant time. Their experiences as part of LGBTQIA+ students can give information to the study. When asked through the guide question, each of them answered relating to each experience.

Table 1 *Participant's Information*

Pseudonym	Sexuality	Gender Identity	Preferred Nouns
Unnelajn	Gay	Non-Binary	He/him
Kiyan	Bisexual	Non-Binary	He/him
Ira	Bisexual	Non-Binary	She/her
Michael Perez	Bisexual	N/A	He/him
Luna	Queer	Non-Binary	She/her
Bini-J	Queer	Gender Fluid	He/him

XD	Pansexual	Non-Binary	They/them
Eleonora	Gay	Gender Fluid	He/him
Marga	Bisexual	Gender Fluid	He/him
Jho	Queer	Non-Binary	He/him

This analysis delves into the complex interplay of sexuality, gender identity, and preferred nouns based on survey data collected from 10 individuals. The findings reveal a nuanced picture of how participants navigate their identities, highlighting the fluidity and diversity within these categories.

The survey identified four individuals who identify as bisexual, two as gay men, three as queer, and one as pansexual. This diversity in sexual orientation reflects the broader spectrum of human sexuality beyond the traditional binary of heterosexual and homosexual. The inclusion of "queer" as a self-identified category is particularly noteworthy, as it often signifies a rejection of rigid labels and an embrace of non-normative identities.

The survey revealed a significant proportion of participants who identify outside the traditional gender binary. Six participants identified as non-binary, three as gender fluid, and one as gender free or ungendered. This demonstrates a growing awareness and acceptance of gender identities beyond the binary of male and female. The presence of "gender fluid" individuals highlights the dynamic and evolving nature of gender identity, while "gender free" or "ungendered" reflects a complete rejection of gender categorization.

The survey also explored participants' preferred nouns, revealing a range of preferences beyond the traditional "he/him" and "she/her" pronouns. Seven participants preferred "he/him," two preferred "she/her," and one preferred "they/them." This finding underscores the importance of respecting individuals' preferred pronouns and recognizing that gender identity is not always reflected in traditional gendered language.

The survey data suggests that participants' identities are not isolated categories but rather interconnected and fluid. For example, while some individuals may identify as bisexual and non-binary, others may identify as gay and gender fluid. This interconnectedness highlights the complexity of individual identity and the need to approach these categories with sensitivity and understanding.

Table 2 *Themes and Core ideas on their Sense of Belonging*

Major Theme	Core Ideas
LGBTQIA+ students' sense of belonging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As a student and we are family. The way they always include me whenever there are competition or contest that is being held in school. Although I don't talk about this much with other people, my friends and classmates are aware of it, and I am grateful that they accept me for who I am and spare no judgment on me. Example when I talk about it to them at first a lot of questions but they are willing to listen and understand me. The people around me who accepted me for who I am. From my experience, most of the students that I encounter at Lapu-Lapu City College does not discriminate any type of gender. There are also students who are like me, so I feel seen. For being who am I. Every time there is a class session knowing all the teachers knew that I am behaving this way, my action differs from my physical appearance yet they still accepted me no matter what. They support my interest and likes. I have never felt humiliated and outcasted from my instructors, they treated me still as a human who dreams big and as their student. I roam around peacefully because this school welcomes everyone including to the group I belong in to. Lapu-Lapu City College has made me feel that I am belong is the environment and the people around me. I felt a sense of belonging as an LGBT individual when my classmates, schoolmates, teachers, and other people treated me with acceptance, respect, and support. As the

newly inducted Educators' Coven president, regardless of my gender, they trust and accept me for who I am, without pulling me down or breaking me, and that's what I love about Lapu-Lapu City College. This acceptance from my friends, co-officers, and teachers really made me feel I belong in the school community.

The mental health challenges faced by LGBTQ+ youth stem from a combination of minority stress, lack of belonging, and societal stigma. Prejudice and discrimination in various social settings, including families, schools, and communities, contribute to feelings of isolation and fear among LGBTQ+ youth. Internalized homophobia and transphobia further exacerbate these challenges, leading to self-doubt and low self-esteem. The societal stigma surrounding LGBTQ+ identities creates a pervasive sense of anxiety and fear, making it difficult for youth to express their true selves without fear of judgment or rejection.

Despite these adversities, the importance of belonging and community support cannot be understated in mitigating the negative impact of minority stress on the mental health of LGBTQ+ youth. A sense of belonging within a supportive community provides validation, acceptance, and a safe space for individuals to connect with others who share similar experiences. Access to community support, such as LGBTQ+ youth groups and organizations, plays a crucial role in fostering friendships, providing resources, and promoting mental well-being.

Addressing the mental health challenges faced by LGBTQ+ youth requires a comprehensive approach that combines individual interventions, community support, and advocacy for policy changes. Therapeutic interventions like cognitive behavioral therapy and mindfulness-based techniques can equip individuals with coping strategies to manage stress and build resilience. Creating inclusive and safe spaces within schools, communities, and families is essential for fostering a sense of belonging and reducing the impact of minority stress. Advocating for policies that protect LGBTQ+ rights, combat discrimination, and promote inclusivity is crucial for creating a more equitable and supportive environment for LGBTQ+ youth to thrive and flourish.

Table 3 *Themes, Ideas on Interaction with the Campus*

Major Theme	Core Ideas
LGBTQIA+ students' interaction on campus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • My classmates • Well I can say that, I'm a very open book to the person that I'm talking with specially to my friends or someone in the campus that I just recently known. For example the new students in our campus and other departments I'm really open in talking to them without any hesitations, because for me I need to be vocal to myself in order for others to be vocal also to me. • In terms of friends and classmates, I can say that interacting with them is just the same as how I interact with 'straight' peeps. Though I can say that I am much more comfortable with my other queer peeps but all in all they're just the same. My interaction with the professors is good but there are times that I can't really express myself well when I'm with them. • Good no problem • By communicating without violence and disrespectful among all students • Sakto lang. Like I can express myself well with my friends and classmates. • I don't normally engage myself not unless they are the one who will come to me. As much as possible, I try to maintain good relationship with everyone to avoid conflict or any kind of misunderstanding. • I am confident and comfortable in interacting to others inside the campus. • I think having an interaction with these people in our campus is like having a family that makes you feel comfortable. • I believe I interact well with those on campus. I usually interact with my classmates with respect and my own principles. I've made many friends on campus. When interacting with teachers, I set boundaries, recognizing that I am

a student and they are teachers. In every interaction, there has been no discrimination regarding my gender.

In the Philippines, LGBT students are frequently the targets of assault and mockery. The findings suggest that LGBTQIA+ students on campus generally experience positive interactions with their peers. Many respondents reported feeling comfortable and open in their interactions with classmates, friends, and even new students, highlighting a sense of inclusivity and acceptance within their social circles. This is further supported by the observation that interactions with classmates are often similar to those with non-LGBTQIA+ individuals, indicating a level of normalcy and integration within the campus community.

While interactions with peers are generally positive, some respondents expressed a sense of caution or reservation when interacting with professors. This suggests a potential for discomfort or a perceived lack of open communication with faculty members. This could be attributed to a number of factors, such as a perceived power dynamic between students and professors, or a lack of awareness or sensitivity regarding LGBTQIA+ issues within the academic setting.

Despite the potential challenges with faculty, the overall sentiment among respondents is one of confidence and comfort in interacting with others on campus. Many expressed a sense of belonging and a feeling of being part of a supportive community. This highlights the importance of fostering a welcoming and inclusive campus environment where LGBTQIA+ students feel safe and supported to express themselves authentically.

Table 4 *Themes, Ideas, experience on Sexual Harassment/ Discrimination Issues*

Major Theme	Core Ideas
Sexual Harassment/ Discrimination Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Well, we cannot deny the fact that there is a discrimination or harassment everywhere. so far, I did not experience it at all It was when the girls who will say (not directly but you can really tell that it's meant for you or something) that they have their own standards, so I better not try make a move on them. Everytime that happens, it annoys me so much. Like, it doesn't mean that when I like girls, I will automatically like them. I have my standards too, no. It doesn't really affect me that much personally, just a bit annoyed to women siguro when they resort to that kind of nonsense logic. I have experience a lot of discrimination. In my high school days there are times my classmates called me "bayot" it is because of my physical actions towards them but I consider all of those discrimination and verbal harassment as a motivation to continue

The responses regarding sexual harassment and discrimination issues reflect a spectrum of experiences among the individuals. While some respondents indicated that they have not encountered any instances of discrimination or harassment, others shared personal accounts of facing discriminatory behavior. One respondent highlighted the annoyance caused by implicit remarks from girls implying that the individual should not make advances towards them due to presumed standards. This experience underscores the impact of subtle forms of discrimination and the frustration it can elicit, even if it does not have a significant personal effect. Additionally, a respondent shared experiences of being called derogatory terms like "bayot" by classmates in high school, citing these instances as discrimination and verbal harassment. Despite encountering such hurtful behaviors, the respondent viewed these challenges as motivation to persevere and continue pursuing their dreams. This resilience in the face of adversity illustrates the strength and determination of individuals who refuse to be defined or deterred by discriminatory actions, using them as fuel to fuel their aspirations and goals.

Overall, while some respondents have not directly experienced sexual harassment or discrimination, the accounts provided shed light on the prevalence of discriminatory attitudes and behaviors in various settings. These narratives emphasize the importance of fostering inclusive and respectful environments where individuals are not judged or mistreated based on their sexual orientation or gender identity. If there is a raising awareness, promoting empathy, and advocating for equality, steps can be taken to address and prevent instances of sexual harassment and discrimination, creating safer and more supportive spaces for all individuals to thrive and be respected.

Findings

The study's findings reveal a complex and nuanced landscape of sexual harassment and discrimination faced by LGBTQIA+ individuals within their communities. Although some respondents reported not encountering instances of

discrimination or harassment, others shared personal accounts that underscore the pervasive nature of discriminatory attitudes and behaviors. These experiences highlight the critical importance of fostering inclusive and respectful environments where individuals are not judged or mistreated based on their sexual orientation or gender identity.

For instance, one respondent recounted an experience where girls made implicit remarks about their standards, suggesting that the respondent should not make advances towards them. While not overtly aggressive, this encounter illustrates the subtle forms of discrimination that can be equally damaging. The respondent's frustration stemmed from the implicit assumption that their attraction to girls automatically meant they would be attracted to everyone, disregarding their personal preferences and standards. This highlights how seemingly innocuous comments can perpetuate harmful stereotypes, reinforcing the notion that LGBTQIA+ individuals are not entitled to the same respect and autonomy as their heterosexual peers.

Another respondent shared a more direct experience of discrimination and verbal harassment, being called derogatory terms like "bayot" by classmates in high school. Despite the deeply hurtful nature of these experiences, the respondent demonstrated remarkable resilience, viewing these challenges as motivation to persevere and continue pursuing their dreams. This resilience underscores the strength and determination of individuals who refuse to be defined or deterred by discriminatory actions, showcasing the human spirit's capacity to overcome adversity and transform negative experiences into opportunities for personal growth.

The absence of direct experiences of harassment or discrimination for some respondents does not negate the reality of these issues in the broader context. These individuals may not have encountered overt acts of discrimination or may have been fortunate to navigate their identities within more supportive environments. Nonetheless, their responses highlight the importance of creating a culture of awareness and sensitivity, ensuring that all individuals feel comfortable sharing their experiences and seeking support when needed.

The narratives shared by respondents suggest the need for a comprehensive, multi-faceted approach to addressing sexual harassment and discrimination:

Education and Awareness

Education is essential in dismantling prejudice and fostering a society where LGBTQIA+ individuals are treated with dignity and respect. Comprehensive and inclusive education about LGBTQIA+ issues should be integrated at all levels of schooling. This education should aim not only to provide factual information about sexual orientation and gender identity but also to cultivate empathy, challenge harmful stereotypes, and encourage critical thinking about the impact of prejudice and discrimination. By exposing individuals to diverse perspectives and experiences, education can help dismantle the misconceptions and biases that often fuel discrimination.

Policy and Legislation

While education is crucial in shaping attitudes, legal frameworks must protect LGBTQIA+ individuals from discrimination and harassment. Policies and legislation should prohibit discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity in all areas of life, including education, employment, housing, healthcare, and public accommodations. These laws should be comprehensive, clearly defining discrimination and harassment and providing mechanisms for reporting and addressing violations. Consistent and effective enforcement is essential to ensure that LGBTQIA+ individuals have access to justice and redress when their rights are violated.

Support Systems

Access to support systems is vital for individuals who have experienced sexual harassment or discrimination. LGBTQIA+ organizations, hotlines, and counseling services play a critical role in providing a safe space for individuals to process their experiences, receive guidance, and access legal or emotional support. These support systems offer a sense of community and belonging, connecting individuals with others who understand their experiences and can provide support and validation. They also provide access to resources, including legal assistance, mental health services, and advocacy support.

Conclusion

The research aimed to assess the perceptions of LGBTQIA+ college students regarding the existence and adequacy of safe spaces within the college. The study used qualitative phenomenological analysis to understand participants' views on existing safe spaces, challenges in accessing supportive environments, and perceptions of inclusivity initiatives at Lapu-Lapu City College.

The study highlights that Lapu-Lapu City College has made significant strides in fostering an inclusive environment for LGBTQIA+ students. The sense of belonging reported by the students is a testament to the supportive school climate. However, the presence of harassment and discrimination are less prevalent indicating that there are still areas for improvement. While most of the students have a positive interaction well on campus, there is still a need for increased knowledge and awareness, particularly among faculty members, to guarantee that all students may express themselves freely and pleasantly.

Recommendations

To create a truly inclusive and positive school climate for LGBTQIA+ students, a multi-faceted approach is essential. Comprehensive anti-discrimination policies should be established, explicitly addressing the needs and rights of LGBTQIA+ students, outlining procedures for reporting incidents, and ensuring appropriate sanctions for violations. This clear framework will foster a sense of security and belonging among LGBTQIA+ students, knowing they are protected and supported.

Integrating LGBTQIA+ issues into the curriculum is crucial for promoting awareness, understanding, and acceptance. This integration should be comprehensive, encompassing various subjects and disciplines, and should highlight the history, rights, and contributions of LGBTQIA+ individuals. This will not only provide a more inclusive educational experience for all students but also challenge harmful stereotypes and foster a more informed and empathetic learning environment.

Furthermore, professional development programs for faculty and staff on LGBTQIA+ issues are vital. These programs should equip educators with the knowledge and skills necessary to create inclusive classroom environments where all students feel respected and valued. Encouraging the formation and support of student-led LGBTQIA+ organizations or groups can provide a vital space for LGBTQIA+ students to connect, build a sense of community, and advocate for their needs. This will foster a sense of belonging and acceptance, creating a more inclusive and supportive campus environment for all.

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Appendix A

Modified Interview Questions

1. What at your school has made you feel like you belong?

Please describe specific experiences, programs, or communities that have contributed to your sense of belonging.

2. Do you think it is easy for you to feel like you belong as someone who is LGBTQIA+ at your school?

Please explain your thoughts and experiences.

3. How do you feel about your school's overall campus climate towards students?

Consider aspects such as inclusivity, support, and general atmosphere.

4. Does your answer change when considering your school campus climate towards LGBTQIA+ students?

Please explain any differences in your perception and the reasons behind them.

5. How well do you think you interact with those on campus?

Consider personal relationships with friends, coworkers, romantic partners, classmates, and staff (e.g., professors, advisors)

6. What are some negative interactions you have experienced?

Please provide details if comfortable.

7. If applicable, please provide a time when you felt targeted by harassment or discrimination because of your sexual orientation or identity.

What was the outcome of this situation, and how did it affect you personally?

8. Do you know anyone who has experienced similar harassment or discrimination?

Please share any relevant experiences.

9. Is there anything you think your school lacks in terms of offerings for students identifying as LGBTQIA+?

This could include programs, resources, or accommodations.

10. What programs or services have you utilized at your school?

Examples include events, health services, academic services, etc.

11. How fulfilled were you with these programs or services?

Please provide specific feedback on your experiences.

12. Lastly, is there anything that researchers have not asked you in this series of questions that you think is important to include in your interview? Feel free to share any additional thoughts or experiences.